

‘All-inclusive AGN’ at the 2024 IAU General Assembly

“Judging from the quality of talks, and topics covered,
I would count this as a very successful meeting!”

Image compilation credit: Sarah White, SAAO

Active galactic nuclei (AGN) play a crucial role in galaxy evolution through a range of feedback processes between the central supermassive black-hole and its surroundings. With the support of the following organisations:

- [IAU Division J](#) (Galaxies and Cosmology)
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... we discussed the latest results in observation- and simulation-driven studies, covering both multi-wavelength and multi-messenger astronomy over a wide range of spatial scales and timescales. In particular, we showcased work that uses southern-hemisphere telescopes such as SALT, MeerKAT, MWA, H.E.S.S., and ALMA. This included exciting results from GRAVITY, which is an optical interferometer on the VLT that is enabling the size of (what is known as) the ‘broad-line region’ to be measured directly for the first time. This has confirmed the ‘Unification Model’ that suggests that most AGN are surrounded by a thick rotating disc of clouds (which is commonly referred to as the dusty ‘torus’, and whose orientation has a significant impact on the observed properties of AGN).

In addition, there were several talks showing how JWST observations are enabling lower-mass supermassive black-holes to be detected at high redshift. These results appear to be in tension with the correlation between black-hole mass and galaxy (i.e. stellar) mass that is seen at lower redshifts. To help explain this, a quite controversial argument was put forward that co-evolution of the black hole and its host galaxy may *not* take place at high redshift, with the latter instead growing at a later time. Some of the many other science highlights included the fact that analytic simulations can now incorporate the turbulence in the galaxy that is created through convection of ‘warm bubbles’ (which are inflated by AGN activity). Zooming in closer to the supermassive black-hole, we learnt that monthly monitoring of nearby ‘radio-loud’ AGN is showing plasmoids

(within the relativistic jet) colliding into each other and eventually having the same polarisation orientation as the outer part of the jet.

This Symposium (hosted in Cape Town, South Africa) was an excellent 5-year follow-up to the first IAU Symposium held in Ethiopia in over 100 years (“Nuclear activity in galaxies across cosmic time”), and so continued to establish and develop international collaborations across and beyond the African continent. Furthermore, we incorporated a discussion on equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) in Astronomy – which is pivotal for the whole community – because researchers may not commonly set aside time to participate in EDI talks or see the relevance of EDI initiatives. Related to this, we are delighted that each of our speaker invitations were accepted, with a gender balance of: 4 female speakers, 2 non-binary (or gender non-specific) speakers, and 4 male speakers.

Out of all of the Symposia and Focus Meetings at the 2024 General Assembly, our Symposium received the highest number of abstracts (300+), which were assessed by our diverse Scientific Organising Committee. We decided that contributed talks should be allocated time-slots of 15 minutes each (so that explanations of the method and findings were not rushed), and this resulted in a total of 40 contributed talks for inclusion in the scientific programme. Final decisions were made by the Chairing Committee (Sarah White, Sthabile Kolwa, and Preeti Kharb), with consideration of scientific merit as well as demographic information (gender, career stage, nationality, and country of residence). The latter enabled us to provide a platform for people that are under-represented at Astronomy conferences, with the aim that the majority of contributions were from delegates in the early stages of their career. We also noted that it is important to record nationality in addition to the country of residence (i.e. affiliation) because the former tends to reflect a person’s ethnicity whereas the latter is modulated by where there is more funding in Astronomy.

Given the high number of submitted abstracts, it was imperative that we scheduled a 90-minute session dedicated to poster-viewing, so that the large number of posters were given sufficient visibility. We are proud to have had 180 participants, both online and in-person. Furthermore, we were highly commended for organising an evening session where all presenters delivered their talks remotely. Not only did this ‘online-first’ approach show respect for our remote attendees, we demonstrated consideration of those in time-zones that differed from SAST (the nominal time-zone for the General Assembly). In addition, we showed that an interactive plenary talk is possible, with our plenary speaker (a fellow Astronomer for Planet Earth) attending online for environmental reasons.

For the full Post-Meeting Report for IAU Symposium 394, please visit <https://www.iau.org/iau/Publications/List-of-Symposia-Reports.aspx>

Written by Sarah White, on behalf of the Chairing Committee...

Chair: Dr Sarah V. White [she] (SAAO, South Africa)

Co-Chair: Dr Sthabile Kolwa [they/she] (University of Johannesburg, South Africa)

Co-Chair: Assoc. Prof. Preeti Kharb [she] (National Centre for Radio Astrophysics, India)

... and the Scientific Organising Committee:

Prof. Tao An [he] (Shanghai Astronomical Observatory [SHAO], China)

Prof. Sara Ellison [she] (University of Victoria, Canada)

Dr Vincenzo Mainieri [he] (European Southern Observatory [ESO], Germany)

Prof. Roberto Maiolino [he] (University of Cambridge, UK)

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Dr Andrea Merloni [he] (Max Planck Institute for Extraterrestrial Physics [MPE], Germany)

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Dr Roderik Overzier [he] (Observatório Nacional, Brazil)

Dr Annalisa Pillepich [she] (Max Planck Institute for Astronomy [MPIA], Germany)

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